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Impacts and Benefits of Pastoral Counselling on Human Wellness in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examines the impacts and benefits of pastoral counselling on human beings, the definition of pastoral counselling, the history of pastoral counselling, the qualifications of a pastoral counsellor, and the uses and benefits of a pastoral counsellor for the wellness of clients. It also looked at the dimensions of health, which are physical, emotional, social, spiritual and intellectual aspects of human beings and factors of the 5F-WELL, which are illustrated in the Indivisible Self as in creative self, coping self, social self, essential self and physical self. The study's participants were 150 from different religious groups and community organisations. A descriptive survey research design was employed, and data was collected and analysed using the mean, standard deviation, and t-test; findings show a positive correlation between the duration of pastoral counselling and spiritual well-being, indicating that more extended engagement in pastoral counselling contributes to a more profound sense of spiritual fulfilment and connection. Pastoral counselling is not for everyone, but it can be a good option for those seeking psychological counselling informed by religious or spiritual ideology and teachings. Recommendations include integrating pastoral counselling with mental health services, implementing specialised training for pastoral counsellors, increasing access to pastoral counselling services, raising public awareness of pastoral counselling and upholding ethical standards.

Keywords: Pastoral Counselling, pastoral counsellor, wellness, 5F-Well factors, Coping Strategies, Ibadan North Local Government Area

Introduction

Religious communities have traditionally sought to provide spiritually-based solutions for those in trouble. For centuries, clergy have listened intently to personal problems and cultivated a spiritual counselling response to those suffering from mental and emotional illness. Traditional spiritual counselling continues to help many of those people. However, it was recognised long

ago that conventional spiritual counselling is only sufficient with classical pastoral counselling experience in many areas such as in the Northern part of Nigeria, Sokoto to be precise and in the South-West of Nigeria during the time of the Colonial Masters.

What is Pastoral Counselling?

Pastoral counselling is a branch of counselling in which psychologically trained ministers, rabbis, priests, imams, and other persons provide therapy services. Pastoral counsellors often integrate modern psychological thought and methods with traditional religious training to address psychospiritual issues in addition to the traditional spectrum of counselling services. (Benner, 2003). Pastoral counselling is a form of psychotherapy that combines both psychology and spirituality. Chinebell (1984) opined that pastoral counselling seeks healing for people suffering from crisis-induced dysfunction and brokenness. The author stated that pastoral counselling is a structured, informed, caring dialogue with people with problems. Unlike religious counsellors, which can be clergy, dull counsellors are trained mental healthcare professionals with in-depth training in religion and theology. Pastoral counselling uses existing psychological and therapeutic models and incorporates faith-based ideas. While individual pastoral counsellors may represent specific religions, the concept and framework of pastoral counselling are not tied to any one religion or faith. Pastoral counselling is a unique form of psychotherapy that uses spiritual resources and psychological understanding for healing and growth (Chinebell, 1984). These ideas were supported by Egan (1994), who strongly opined that people sought help when they could not handle problematic situations properly. These problems show up in various ways, that is, in relationships, in marriage, amongst siblings, in the workplace, through a traumatic experience, for example, being raped, robbed, hijacked and nowadays divorced. Summarily, pastoral counselling:

- i. Focuses on people with problems;
- ii. The field requires expert knowledge, which sanitised training;
- iii. Involves redemptive and therapeutic dialogue (Egan, 1994).

Statement of the Problem

Despite the widespread availability of various forms of psychological and therapeutic support, there needs to be more understanding and recognition of the specific impacts that pastoral counselling has on human well-being. This form of counselling, which integrates spiritual guidance with psychological care, offers a unique approach to addressing emotional, mental, and spiritual challenges. However, the extent of its effectiveness and the way it contributes to overall well-being need to be well-documented and studied. This study seeks to bridge this gap by exploring the impacts and benefits of pastoral counselling on individuals' holistic health.

Research Hypotheses

- **Hypothesis 1** Individuals who receive pastoral counselling will exhibit significantly more significant improvements in emotional and psychological well-being than those who do not accept any form of counselling.

- **Hypothesis 2** Participants who undergo pastoral counselling will report higher levels of spiritual well-being than those who do not.
- **Hypothesis 3** The duration and frequency of pastoral counselling sessions positively correlate with overall life satisfaction and perceived quality of life.

Methodology

Research Design

The study used a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative research methods to comprehensively understand the impacts and benefits on human well-being in Ibadan North Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria.

Participants

- **Sample Size:** The study involved 150 participants for a robust analysis
- **Selection Criteria:** Participants include 80 individuals (40 Christians and 40 Muslims) who had undergone pastoral counselling within the last year. A control group of 40 individuals (20 Christians and 20 Muslims) who had not received any form of counselling during the same period were also involved for comparison.
- **Recruitment:** Participants were recruited from Christ Apostolic Church (CAC) Oke Agbara, Ashi-Basorun, and NASFAT Society at Samonda, beside the University of Ibadan, in the Ibadan North Local Government of Oyo State, Nigeria.

Surveys and Questionnaires: Structured instruments such as the Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale (DASS-21), the Spiritual Wellbeing Scale (SWBS), and the Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) were administered to assess psychological, emotional, and spiritual well-being.

In-Depth Interview: Semi-structured interviews were conducted with a subset of 30 participants (15 Christians and 15 Muslims) to gain deeper insights into their pastoral experiences with pastoral counselling.

Focus Groups: Small groups of 6-8 participants were organised to discuss the perceived benefits and impacts of pastoral counselling, facilitating rich and interactive discussions. Techniques such as t-tests, ANOVA, and regression analysis were used to compare the well-being measures between the counselling and control groups.

The History of Pastoral Counselling

People have long turned to religious leaders for support, guidance and solutions related to mental health issues, and ministers of all denominations traditionally provide counselling to members of their religious communities. Pastoral counselling was born from the idea that, although this kind of support is valuable, some issues may require more professional help. (Griffith & Young, 1987). In the early 1900s, Reverend Anton Boison, one of the founders of the Pastoral Education Movement, pioneered a unique enrichment program in which he connected theology students with hospital patients who were also experiencing concerns of a psychiatric nature. In the early 1930s, Minister Vincent Peale and psychiatrist Smiley Blanton formed the American Foundation of Religion and Psychiatry, known today as the Blanton-Peale Institution. Clinical pastoral education programs like these laid the foundation for the pastoral counselling field, which

evolved over the next several decades as more and more clergy members sought formal training in psychology. (American Association of Pastoral Counsellors, 2020).

Required Qualifications for Being a Pastoral Counsellor

Pastoral counsellors are certified mental healthcare professionals with extensive religious education and training. It is common for pastoral counsellors to be licensed Marriage and Family Therapists (LMFTs) or Clinical Professional Counsellors (LCPCs). Below are some qualifications of a pastoral counsellor:

- A bachelor's degree;
- A master's or doctoral degree;
- A master's or doctoral degree in the mental health field

What is Pastoral Counselling Used For?

As with other mental healthcare professionals, pastoral counsellors can help with various issues and often have extraordinary marriage and family therapy, substance use disorders, or mental health conditions. They can also help with spiritual or religious matters. Some areas pastoral counselling may address include;

- Grieving the loss of a loved one
- Coping with illness
- Handling significant insignificant challenges, times of transition or life crisis
- Parenting difficulties
- Preparing for marriage or adjusting to divorce
- Mental health disorder treatment
- Processing difficult or traumatic life events
- Counselling for all ages and couples and family
- Integrating faith with daily life
- Strengthening relationships include, ng with oneself and with God
- Wellness programs
- Spiritual direction
- Outreach preventive services such as in prison, military settings and schools
- Community Education (Michael, 2000).

Wellness in Pastoral counselling

Wellness is a dynamic process of physical, mental, and spiritual optimisation and integration, which is the outcome of that process. Bill Hettler (1984), the father of the modern wellness movement, defined wellness as 'an active process through which people become aware of and make choices toward a more successful existence. Myers, Sweeney, and Witmer (2000) also concluded that wellness is a way of life oriented toward optimal well-being. In that body, mind and spirit are integrated by the individual to live more fully within the human and natural community. Ideally, each individual can achieve the optimum state of health and well-being.

Dimensions of Wellness

There are five aspects of personal well-being: physical, emotional, social, spiritual, and intellectual. All five areas must be addressed to be considered healthy.

Physical Wellness

1. Regular exercise, such as walking 30 minutes daily, will significantly improve one's health.
2. Eat healthy. Avoid fried foods, soft drinks, processed meats, and sweets. Include fruits and vegetables in your diet every day.
3. Make sure to eat all meals, especially breakfast.
4. Avoid heavy episodic drinking and drug use.
5. Get at least 6-8 hours of sleep every night.

Emotional Wellness

- i. Maintain a positive attitude even when problems arise.
- ii. Discovering one's stress reliever and managing time wisely can lower stress.
- iii. Share information with a trusted person
- iv. Smile even when one does not feel like improving emotional wellness.

Social Wellness

- i. Balance social life with academic responsibility.
- ii. Choose a good and resourceful friend.
- iii. Recognize when in an unhealthy relationship.

Spiritual Wellness

- i. Find a quiet place to meditate every day
- ii. Contemplate the meaning of life.
- iii. Appreciate the natural world.

Intellectual Wellness

- i. Keep abreast of current affairs
- ii. Seek academic help always
- iii. Become a lifelong learner (Bill, 1984)

Five-Factor Wellness (5F-WELL)

According to Jane, Myers, and Sweeney (2005), the Five Factor Wellness Inventory (FFWEL) is an evidence-based tool for assessing wellness characteristics and helping individuals make choices for healthier living.

Creative Self

- **Thinking:** Being mentally active, open-minded, creative and experimental, having a sense of curiosity, and applying problem-solving strategies to social conflicts.

- **Emotions:** Being aware of or in touch with one's feelings. Ability to express appropriately positive and negative feelings.
- **Control:** Belief about one's competence, confidence and personal mastery, beliefs that one can usually achieve the goals set for himself.
- **Work:** Satisfaction with one's work, feeling that one's skills are used and appreciated, feeling one can manage one's workload, feeling a sense of job security, and feeling appreciated in the work none does.
- **Cheerful humour:** Being able to laugh at one's mistakes and use humour to accomplish even serious tasks.

Coping Self

- **Leisure:** Satisfaction with leisure time, feeling that one's skills are used appropriately.
- **Stress Management involves ongoing** self-assessment of one's coping resources and the ability to organise/manage resources such as time, energy, and setting limits.
- **Self-worth:** Accepting who and what one is, positive qualities, imperfections, and a sense of being genuine within oneself and others.
- **Realistic Beliefs:** Ability to process information and perceive reality accurately, absence of persistent, irrational beliefs and thoughts and need for perfection.

Social Self

- **Friendships are social** relationships that involve a connection with others individually or in the community but do not have a marital, sexual, or familiar commitment. Friendship requires empathy for others and feeling understood by others.
- **Love:** The ability to be intimate, trusting, self-disclosing with another, giving as well as expressing affection to significant others, and accepting others without conditions.
- **Spirituality:** Personal beliefs and behaviours practised as part of the recognition that we are more than the material aspects of mind and body, faith in a higher power, hope and optimism, the practice of worship, and prayer. And meditation, purpose in life, compassion for others, moral values and transcendence (a sense of oneness with the universe).
- **Gender Identity:** Satisfaction with and feeling supported in one's gender, ability to be androgynous.
- **Cultural identity:** Satisfaction and feeling supported in one's cultural identity, cultural assimilation.
- **Self-Care:** Taking responsibility for wellness through preventive self-care and safety habits.

Physical Self

- **Nutrition:** Eating a nutritionally balanced diet, maintaining an average weight within 15% of the ideal.
- **Exercise:** Engaging in sufficient physical activity through exercise or work to maintain good physical condition. Jane, et al. (2005).

Procedure

The Participants of this study were randomly drawn from members of the Christ Apostolic Church (CAC) Oke Agbara, Ashi-Basorun in Ibadan and from members of Nasfat Society, Samonda beside University of Ibadan in Ibadan North Local Government of Oyo State, Nigeria. **Hypothesis 1** states that Individuals who receive pastoral counselling will exhibit significantly more improvements in emotional and psychological well-being than those who do not accept any form of counselling.

Table 1 Comparison of receivers of pastoral counselling and those who did not receive it on emotional and psychological wellbeing

Variables	N	X	SD	DF	T-abs	T-Crit	P
Receiver of pastoral counselling	85	48.50	8.389	298	1.18	0.96	****
Did not receive pastoral counselling	65	48.70	9.857				

The above result shows that the differences in emotional and psychological well-being between the counselling and control groups were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) since the computed t-value (1.18) is greater than the t-critical value (0.96). This is an indication that pastoral counselling has an impact on the emotional and psychological well-being of the individuals.

Hypothesis 2 states that Participants who undergo pastoral counselling will report higher levels of spiritual well-being than those who do not.

Table 2 Comparison of participants who undergo pastoral counselling reporting higher levels of spiritual well-being than those who do not.

Variables	N	X	SD	DF	T-obs	T-Crit	P
With pastoral counseling	60	37.005	5.291	298	1.96	1.74	****
No pastoral counselling	90	38.071	4.785				

The results from Table 2 above show a significant difference in the level of spiritual well-being of participants who underwent pastoral counselling, reflecting enhanced spiritual health compared to those who did not. The observed values (1.96) are more significant than the t-critical (1.74).

This indicates that pastoral counselling participants reported higher spiritual and life satisfaction levels than the control Groups.

Hypothesis 3 states that the duration and frequency of pastoral counselling sessions positively correlate with overall life satisfaction and perceived quality of life.

Table 3 compares the duration and frequency of pastoral counselling sessions, which positively correlates with overall life satisfaction and perceived quality of life.

Variables	N	X	SD	DF	Obs -t	Crit-t	P
Long duration and more frequency	55	31.1448	6.000	298	2.93	1.96	*****
Low duration and short frequency	95	38.071	5.900				

The results from Table 3 show a positive correlation between the duration of pastoral counselling and spiritual well-being, suggesting that more extended engagement in pastoral counselling contributes to a more profound sense of spiritual fulfilment and connection.

Discussion of Findings

Qualitative Findings

Common themes emerged from the interviews, including increased hope, emotional relief and a stronger sense of purpose. Participants often described pastoral counselling as a unique source of comfort and guidance that addressed their emotional and spiritual needs. Participants in the focus group highlighted the importance of the spiritual dimension in their healing process, noting that pastoral counselling provided a holistic approach that traditional counselling sometimes needed to improve. Many shared their experiences of overcoming significant life crises with the help of their counsellors. Participants identified several techniques as particularly beneficial, including prayers, scripture reading, and spiritual reflections, combined with traditional therapeutic methods such as cognitive-behavioural strategies. The pastoral counselling environment was also described as compassionate and non-judgmental, fostering a safe space for individuals to express their deepest concerns and explore solutions.

Conclusion

Psychology uses scientific language to discuss human beings and behaviours, whereas pastoral counselling discusses human beings, their relations with fellow beings, and the spiritual aspects of wellness. Pastoral counselling combines psychology and religion. Pastoral counsellors are

mental healthcare professionals with associated privileges and responsibilities. They are also educated and trained in religion and theology (Adebayo & Kolawole, 2013).

Counselling provided by religious leaders in Christ Apostolic Church and Nasfat Society differs from pastoral counselling because they lack the appropriate orientation required by mental healthcare professionals. Pastoral counselling is not for everyone, but it can be a good option for those seeking psychological counselling informed by religious or spiritual ideology and teachings. Ensuring one's pastoral counsellor's beliefs align with one's needs is essential. Ask about the counsellor's views before beginning counselling, and try a different counsellor if they are not a good fit.

Recommendations

1. Foster collaboration between pastoral counsellors and mental health professionals to create a more holistic approach to care.
2. Implement specialised training programs for pastoral counsellors that include psychological principles and therapeutic techniques.
3. Promote the availability of pastoral counselling, especially in underserved and rural areas, through funding initiatives and partnerships with community organisations.
4. Launch public awareness to educate the public about the benefits of pastoral counselling, emphasising how it addresses both spiritual and psychological needs to improve overall well-being.
5. Tailor pastoral counselling to the client's needs by understanding their unique spiritual and psychological context.
6. Ensure pastoral counsellors adhere to strict ethical standards, including confidentiality, informed consent, and professional boundaries. Regular training on moral issues should be mandatory to maintain trust and professionalism.

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